

New Army Method in Stating and Assessing RAM Requirements

L. K. Jokubaitis U. S. Army TACOM Warren

M. F. Quinn U. S. Army TACOM Warren

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SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

As history has shown, the establishment of reliability requirements for complex equipment operating under diversified and difficult environments is a challenging task. It is challenging to a point where a singular mission requirement expressed in generalized terms does not do the job. For this reason, the recently introduced U. S. Army methodology of specifying reliability both to assess its performance during a given mission and to determine the quality of the product with more all-inclusive logistics overtones covers all the aspects of reliability concerns. Additionally, the dictated approach to specify reliability in terms of reliability growth and bands minimizes the danger of beating a system to death without appropriate evaluation or a chance to establish its worthiness. The associated improvements in the techniques to assess reliability and to identify candidates for minimizing logistics burden and for approving cost-effectiveness will also enhance the quality of the product. The thrust of this effort has been, and is, to provide the most reliable equipment to the soldier in the field without shooting oneself in the foot during the process due to poor reliability specifications or assessment techniques.

1. INTRODUCTION

The recent conflict in Southwest Asia was a graphic example of the increasing complexity of modern weapon systems. It also illustrated the unchanging harshness of the environments in which these technological marvels must operate. The increasing problem of developing high tech systems to function in hostile environments is most evident in U. S. Army ground equipment. The modern armored combat weapon system - - tank - - is an example. Here we have space age navigation, target acquisition, and communications systems subjected to the extremes of climatic variables and the vibrations and shock loads found only in a tracked vehicle weighing over 100,000 lbs at highway speeds over rough ground.

Under these circumstances, it is not surprising that these vehicles experience many "failures." Some of these are corrected by merely tightening a screw; others may require a complete overhaul. This is viewing the "failure" in terms of the required corrective action. Another way of looking at "failure" is with respect to their impact on the function of the system. In the case

of tanks, it is the impact of the "failure" on the ability of the system to perform its assigned missions. This impact on performance may be anything from a slight reduction in top speed to complete immobilization. Certainly the minor incapacities cannot be ignored; but, just as certainly, they should not be counted together with the disastrous incapacities as "failures" of the system.

And they will be counted. Weapon systems of today are subject to critical appraisals from concept through development and fielding until they are retired from service. There is also an ever increasing interest in the logistic burden associated with a given system, and the operational and support cost of the weapon systems. For this reason, the reliability requirements cannot be constrained only to the critical failures associated with mission performance. They must also address the total spectrum of reliability and maintainability - - from the failures affecting the logistics posture to the failures affecting the system performance to failures affecting the capability to perform during a mission.

Needless to say, a simplistic approach to RAM specification and assessment is an invitation to continuous misunderstanding as a weapon system is developed. For this reason, it was determined to come up with a new and better method for the new Main Battle Tank programs. The first program selected to experience this new methodology is the Armored Gun System (AGS) which is a light version offshoot from the Main Battle Tank programs.

The emerging methodology utilizes a dual approach to reliability requirements - - one geared to the combat interests in mission survival, and one geared to a more inclusive reliability consideration which allows for assessing reliability in terms of logistics and cost-effectiveness. This definition is also better for applying reliability principles during the design phase, and even in applying reliability incentives in the contractual arrangements to optimize the reliability posture.

2. DEFINING RAM ATTRIBUTES

Historically, the Army has lost some of its best systems not from enemy action but by being shot down in the formative stages by budget experts and oversight committees due to the wrong perception that the systems were unreliable - - that they fell short

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of their specified mean time between failure. This perception is usually due to one of two reasons. One of the reasons is the misunderstanding associated with the phenomenon of reliability growth. The other reason is the "shooting yourself in the foot" syndrome whereby the Army establishes reliability requirements based on the infrequently experienced mission failures, and then assesses reliability by including other, less significant, failures. This problem arises when the failure definitions are too generalized and liberties are taken during the requirement phase to establish unrealistic requirements in order to "push the developer," and then minor failures are charged during test scoring by the user/tester in order to "push for corrective actions." The intent is good, but the end result is controversy that creates misunderstanding and dead programs. Here the difficulty comes from comparing RAM measurements made during the early development cycle to the specified RAM characteristics that can be expected of a mature, fully developed system. This puts the program office in the defensive position of trying to explain through reliability growth projections and other methods why the early test values, though low, are acceptable and the system will grow and meet its specified value when fielded. To the typical layman, this type of analysis seems like an excuse for nonperformance. At best, it raises questions; at worst, it provides ammunition to shoot down projects and attack the credibility of the developers.

Looking back at history during the 1950s and 1960s, the U.S. Army failure definition and the associated reliability requirements were very ambiguous and undefined. Many of the requirements were limited to subjective statements such as "more reliable than previous systems," or in some cases the requirements were overstated by a factor of 2, 3, or sometimes even 10. Some systems were terminated due to misunderstanding and the obvious inability to satisfy the overstated requirements. For this reason, during the early 1970s, TACOM invented and applied an approach identified as the Mission Reliability Factor (MRF) concept. Under this concept, specific failure modes were assigned factors ranging from 0.1 to 1.0 which were based on either the expected effect on a particular mission by that failure mode or the criticality of that effect. This methodology worked fairly well, and such systems as the Abrams Main Battle Tank and Bradley Infantry Weapon System were designed and proven to be reliable systems through the utilization of this methodology. Unfortunately, this methodology was plagued by controversy and misunderstanding since some personnel could not understand the utilization of "partial failures." Therefore, in 1980 this methodology was banned and substituted by a generalized definition of a mission reliability and the use of scoring conferences to thrash out and argue the chargeability of failures observed during test. This approach worked fairly well for non-complex tactical systems. However, when the concept for the new Main Battle Tanks was considered, it became apparent that it would not work, and that the problems would revert back to the ones experienced during the 1950s and 60s.

Specifically, for the Block III Tank, one of the variants of the new Main Battle Tank family, the user wanted to establish reliability requirements that were a significant improvement

over the M1 Tank it was intended to replace. At the same time, the agency charged with evaluation of new systems was insisting on the existing failure definition that encompassed minor incidents as well as the mission abort incidents that were the basis of reliability specification of the superseded M1 Tank.

There was obvious need to study the problem and to develop a reasonable solution. Accordingly, in early 1990, a team was formed with representation from the developing agency, the troop users, and the test & evaluation agencies to address the issues and to develop a comprehensive failure definition methodology.

3. SPECIFYING RELIABILITY

The team set about its herculean task of developing an approach to reliability specifications that would satisfy the concerns of all affected parties. They had to operate under both technical and nontechnical constraints. The results of their work could not have numbers that were too low in comparison with prior systems (regardless of the underlying differences in system complexities or assigned definition of terms). This would be politically unsellable, and could kill a program before it got started. Conversely, if too high, the values could not be validly tested within the budget constraints.

To move from theoretical discussions to real world needs, the multi-agency committee was given the specific task of developing reliability specifications for the Armored Gun System (AGS), one of the family of emerging Armored Force Modernization systems.

What the team faced can be best illustrated by Figure 1 where the total perspective of failures ranging from all-inclusive events to the very selective critical events are shown. The general definitions are as follows:

- **Catastrophic Failure** - Any malfunction that would abort the start or completion of a battlefield mission due to a malfunction that represents a threat to the safety of the vehicle or crew member.
- **Mission Degrading Failures** - Any malfunction that severely degrades the mission to a point where it has to be aborted. The effect differs by types of missions, extent of degradation allowed, and available redundancies. Requires complex matrices and controversial agreements.
- **Mission Affecting Failures** - Any malfunction that has impact (no matter how minor) on the performance specification. Does not allow any performance degradation or redundancy. Establishes the "Quality of the Product."
- **Maintenance Essential Actions** - Any malfunction that requires corrective action at the first possible opportunity.
- **Unscheduled Maintenance Action** - Any observation that results in unscheduled maintenance action.

Depending on the definition of failure that is chosen, the reasonable MTBF might range from 50 mean miles between failure to 700 mean miles between failure.

In the administration of a reliability program, the two extremes are relatively easy to define and test for compliance. Unfortunately, neither one of these extremes by themselves can serve as a satisfactory requirement in the pursuit of a viable reliability program. The catastrophic failures are too restrictive and require extensive tests to demonstrate, and do not answer the questions of logistics burden as cost-effectiveness. The all inclusive unscheduled maintenance actions are too insignificant and numerous, and do not answer the question of criticality to a system's performance. Therefore, the failures that degrade a system's performance and in this manner have a certain effect on the mission are the ones to pursue and define. However, this is where the dilemma becomes apparent. How do you define the extent of allowable degradation? How do you treat redundancy? How do you measure a decrease in performance? What is essential maintenance? Experience has taught us that when these definitions are used, they need an inch thick document that expands on the definition in minute detail. And still there are arguments.

As the developing agency, TACOM has specific concerns. As noted above, it is important that there is a match between the reliability requirement that is established for a system and the failure definition. We also need a comprehensive up-front failure definition. This must:

- Not be left until the test results are being analyzed when a whole set of prejudices come into play.
- Be definitive on allowable mission degradation and impact of redundancies.
- Have concurrence from the developer, the user, and subsequently the contractor.
- Adequately serve for measurement of program concerns such as weapon system availability, operating and support cost, and contractual RAM incentives.

With these considerations in mind it was decided to utilize three failure definitions to meet all needs. As seen in Figure 2, the selected definitions included the all inclusive unscheduled maintenance actions, the mission affecting failures, and the mission abort failures with allowed and defined degradation levels. Any and all malfunctions that resulted in unscheduled maintenance was chosen so that maintenance burden and operating and support costs could be tracked. At the other extreme, the mission abort failure category with allowable degradation factors would serve the needs of the doctrine and tactics personnel because it was directly tied to operational availability and probability of mission success. The higher number associated with this failure definition would also make the program more attractive at the innumerable reviews that are part of all major programs. The third, middle, reliability failure definition is most

valuable in contractual dealings. It relates to hardware performance parameters that are meaningful to engineers. It can be used in specifications relative to design-in and built-in reliability around which reliability incentive clauses can be built into procurement contracts.

The UMA failure definition is obvious. Making a distinction between the MA (Mission Abort) and MAF (Mission Affecting Failure) is less apparent. Figure 3 illustrates how some component failures would be evaluated in making the decision of calling these failures an MA or MAF type. In this example, a failure of either the gunner's primary sight or gunner's auxiliary sight constitutes a mission affecting failure. However, in order to be charged a mission abort failure, both of these components would have to fail. Why? Because the mission can be successfully carried out by utilizing either one of these components. It's a question of redundancy. The commander's weapon status sight is a similar example where the commander can visually perform the task. In the case of the torsion bars, the system can successfully operate at a degraded mode with a failure of any torsion bar except when both #1 and #6 break. In that case, the tank is immobilized and the mission would be aborted. In this manner, a matrix can be prepared defining all the pertinent failure modes and their chargeability and provide as a part of the requirement documents. This will not preclude all the arguments, but it certainly will aid in understanding the rationale behind the requirement and facilitate the scoring of the test results.

Top management in the Army was acutely aware of the problems of rational reliability specifications. They had been kept abreast of the ad hoc committee's deliberations and findings by frequent briefings. In February of 1991, a joint position was issued by the Commanding General of the Army Materiel Command and the Commanding General of the Training and Doctrine Command. This directed that reliability requirements be expressed in accordance with three rules:

1. Requirements will be realistic.
2. Requirements will be expressed as bands (when appropriate).
3. Requirements will be matched to the system's maturity level.

Shown graphically, these principles are depicted in Figure 4. Here the new system requirement is established at Initial Operational Capability (IOC) time frame by evaluating the baseline system performance and by indicating the new system median prediction by allowing a 10 to 30% state-of-the-art improvement. A band is established by allowing a plus and minus 10% tolerance. Of course, these values can be adjusted and modified if proof exists for a specific need to do this. Then a reliability growth curve is plotted to the beginning of the program by utilizing a historically acceptable slope. This slope is usually 0.3 for a developmental program and 0.2 for a quasi-NDI program. Some growth may be as small as 0.1 if the system is not expected to undergo a significant developmental phase. As

a final step, specific test thresholds can be established by modifying the reliability growth band for a given test frame by considering appropriate developers' risk factors. Of course the customer may also be interested in establishing a certain confidence factor which, in fact, may negate the developer's threshold and establish the requirements within the original reliability growth band.

How this relates to an individual system requirement is shown in Figure 5. This is a draft of the AGS requirements. Here one can see that:

- Maturity level is taken into account in the reliability specification.

- Both Mission Abort and Mission Performance.

- Affecting failures are taken into account.

- Both hardware related failures as well as total operational failures are specified. The operational failures include such events as failures caused due to poor training, maintenance and operator faults.

- The total maintenance burden is addressed by a maintenance ratio (Maintenance Man Hours- Operating Hours) call out.

In summary, the most significant changes made in the new Army methodology for specifying reliability are as follows:

1. There are two distinct reliability requirements; one to define the system's ability to start and complete a mission without experiencing an abort. The other considers the systems and its component's reliability as it relates to the performance specification. There is also a third reliability requirement which is integrated into the maintenance ratio requirement. Here the definition is all-inclusive and the concern is logistics burden and the operational and support cost.

2. The failure modes and chargeability for same is shown as part of a matrix that is included as part of the requirements document.

3. The requirements documents also identify and project the expected reliability growth, in effect establishing a specific lower requirement for the various test frames. The requirement may also be expressed as a band where there is a significant difference between the minimum acceptable value and the best possible value. This is most appropriate for development systems with significant uncertainty in the requirement accuracy.

4. TRACKING RELIABILITY

In conjunction with the new methodologies in establishing and specifying reliability requirements, steps have been taken to improve the assessment and analysis techniques. This is both true for assessing test information and field information. In regards to the test information, software has been developed

under contract with Failure Analysis Associates, Inc., identified as Hyper RAM. This software facilitates test control and provides automatic plotting of the reliability growth that is experienced as the test progresses. In this manner, the status of reliability at any time during test is automatically projected on a PC against the predicted and projected reliability growth/band. The 90% confidence bands are also computed and identified on the screen. These software capabilities include the abilities to:

1. Prepare planned reliability growth curves for systems before development testing has begun, based on design characteristics and material data.

2. Monitor reliability and reliability growth throughout the development phase in order to quantitatively assess progress toward the achievement of a specific reliability goal and, ultimately, to obtain a quantified certification that the goal has been achieved.

3. Identify variances between actual and planned reliability growth during development in order to enable early program reduction to achieve RAM goals.

4. Predict the number of test hours and amount of development time that shall most likely be required, under a given reliability management plan, to achieve a specified level of reliability.

5. Consolidate estimates of system's reliability obtained during development tests with the reliability of the same system under actual field conditions.

In regards to the field data, TACOM has recently developed and established a system identified as the Fielded Vehicle Performance Data System (FVPDS). This system incorporates and integrates all the available field data systems in order to assess the latest field reliability status. This data is projected on screens and automatically compared to the previously experienced test information. In this manner, the reliability posture is determined and weak links are identified for potential design improvements and reduction in the operational and support costs. Consideration is being given within feasible contractual and legal bounds to tie-in this information with Government-Industry Data Exchange Program (GIDEP) in order to provide the Army combat and tactical vehicle reliability status to industry for possible design improvement considerations. The availability of this data will also aid the industry in determining vehicle component reliability rates, and utilizing same for their predictions and new system reliability determinations.

These improvements in assessing and displaying test and field reliability data in conjunction with the establishment of more comprehensive reliability specification parameters will aid the U. S. Army in the quest of pursuing and obtaining reliable and cost-effective equipment. In this manner, the excellent performance already displayed by U. S. Army equipment during Desert Storm can be maintained and further enhanced.

5. PROVIDING INCENTIVES

Once the RAM attributes are specified in the system specification, all that remains is to see that the contractors who develop and manufacture the system will meet or better the specified levels. This is said facetiously because we all know that this is the truly difficult part of RAM management. Historically, in the course of meeting schedule and cost commitments, the contractors are prone to give short shrift to meeting RAM goals, let alone exceeding them. Therefore, as an adjunct to our studies on how to best define the RAM, an effort was launched to overcome this traditional lack of contractor focus on this essential system characteristic. Incentivizing reliability if you will.

As of this writing nothing has been finalized on any of the ASM systems. We have, however, been studying the various considerations and methods that can be used to focus contractors on RAM. Both monetary and non-monetary incentives are under study. First, a few words about the latter. These can be used for both the contractors and the government program offices. Two we have looked at are management oriented and technology oriented. Management awards might consider such things as program leadership, planning effectiveness, manpower utilization, good acquisition, etc. Technical awards could consider technical accomplishments with respect to contribution to the immediate program, projected value to LCC (life cycle cost), contribution to the state-of-the-art, etc.

Advantages of non-monetary awards include their low cost (principally their administration) and their flexibility - e.g., they can be instituted and/or dropped without any contract changes. Because of this flexibility and because of their lesser impact, work on the non-monetary incentives have not been dropped but have certainly subordinated to the monetary incentives in our current studies.

Because the contractors involved are almost always profit oriented organizations, monetary incentives are probably going to best get their attention. And, if properly formulated, they can get the contractors to focus on the RAM characteristics of primary interest. There are three things that must be taken into account when planning a monetary incentive program for getting the desired response from contractors. First, the parameters upon which the incentives are based must be unambiguous. Secondly, the goals upon which the incentives are based must be realistic. And thirdly, the incentive program should be adaptable to mainstream system development activities and schedules to minimize administrative cost and complexity.

At present we are inclined toward incentive bonus payments for achieving desired levels of RAM during the development period and then incentivizing via warranty provisions during the production phase. As shown in Figure 6 we can base reliability growth incentives during design based upon the specific results of two key development tests and warranty during the production/deployment period.

The method of defining and specifying RAM that was discussed earlier fits in very well with an incentive program.

First, the definitions are unambiguous. Secondly, since the reliability requirements are specified on the concept of reliability growth, it is consistent with real life.

And finally, this approach allows incentives to be awarded realistically based on RAM measurements during key development tests.

This is illustrated in Figure 7. This shows how a realistic value for RAM is specified not as a point but as an increasing band. In this example the band is based on values plus or minus 10% from a median value that is set at 10-30% higher than state-of-the-art. At the conclusion of each of the two major development tests, the contractor is eligible for incentive awards that will increase based on demonstrated achievement of RAM levels above the threshold. At the other extreme, the developer's risk is a moderate 10%.

6. TRACKING GROWTH

Reliability measurement is important in all development programs, but it is particularly important when tracking reliability growth. And it is absolutely essential that RAM measurement schemes are in place on development programs that have monetary incentive programs. Fortunately, the Army has good systems in place to meet this need.

As noted in Figure 8, government test sites have an in-place system for feeding test information into the Automated Data Collection System (ADACS). Each and every time any maintenance action is performed on a system under test, a detailed description is written up on a Test Information Report (TIR). This is a complete exposition of all aspects of the action including parts affected, man hours and clock hours if maintenance required, and all other aspects of interest to a RAM analyst. The TIR with a preliminary failure score assigned is put into the ADACS data base. This data base is available to all government agencies involved in the program as well as the contractors. The failure is verified or certified when these recipients of the data meet during a failure scoring conference. Any adjustments or revisions to the preliminary scoring are recorded, and the TIR is amended so that the ADACS data base reflects this official RAM scoring.

During the course of the test the RAM characteristics of interest are plotted. These will vary as might be expected. But as the test continues, the true values become more clearly defined. On long tests (some may exceed a year in length) there is often the opportunity to incorporate reliability improvements in the system under test during the test cycle. This allows for the plotting of RAM growth. Using mathematical techniques developed by the Army Material System Analysis Agency (AMSAA), reasonable projection of RAM growth can be developed.

As discussed previously, reliability growth does not end when a system goes into production and is released to the field.

Usually the design engineering function continues during the early production phase to continue the product improvement that could not be accomplished during the limited time allowed in the development cycle, and to correct problems that surface only after field use. It is during this phase that a system finally achieves its mature level of RAM. It is also during this time that monetary incentives based on warranty guarantees come into play. Tracking RAM parameters at this time are very important, but measurements in the field are very difficult.

The principal system for tracking RAM in the field is Sample Data Collection which is usually referred to by its acronym SDC. This involves the careful follow-up on a selected group of systems at selected field sites. The selections are made to get data on a relatively few systems that truly represent the total population. This selected sample is then tracked by a representative of a data collection contractor. The individual representatives are most often retired warrant officers or noncoms with experience in the field operation in which the target systems are being used. The desire is to duplicate the quality and detail of the reports from development test. But as one would expect, this is not achieved on data collected in the field.

As reported in the newspapers recently, the U.S. Census Bureau can give testimony to the problems in collecting information in the field. Also reported in the news articles about the recent census count is the fact that the Census Bureau has developed statistical techniques to correct for the errors in the raw data. This is how they determined that there was an error of approximately 2% - 5,000,000 in a total count of approximately 250,000,000. In the same way we can purify the raw SDC data. Through experience gained from contracts to analyze SDC data, scientists at Battelle Memorial Laboratory have developed statistical procedures for testing raw SDC data. As shown in Figure 9, these procedures are used to purify the raw data inputs from the field. Only after this adjustment/selection are the data used in the RAM analyses. As shown in this figure, these data are also used to determine Operating and Support (O&S) costs related to sustainment of the system in the field.

7. STATUS

The U. S. Army has embarked on a program to completely update our combat weapon systems. This program has the acronym ASM for Armored System Modernization. This activity will equip our armed forces with a family of armored vehicles that are being developed from the ground up. They will incorporate the newest technology in power trains, electronics, and weaponry, and they will benefit from the best RAM management methods.

The process of RAM definition and specification described here is being used to insure that the RAM characteristics of these weapon systems will be as attractive as their other performance values. Incentives and management methods are being developed to maintain a clear focus on RAM objectives.

The administration mechanics of implementing and managing RAM is undergoing a shake out on a current weapon

system development program on a mobile armored gun. As in the introduction of any new procedure, there are problems. But with the help of a lot of people from many Army agencies, these are being improved to everyone's satisfaction. We are convinced that the next generation of Army vehicles will benefit from the latest and best in RAM technology as well as the latest and best in hardware.

BIOGRAPHIES

Leonas K. Jokubaitis
Chief, RAM/Assessment and Data Division
U. S. Army Tank-Automotive Command
ATTN: AMSTA-QR
Warren, Michigan 48397-5000 USA

Mr. Jokubaitis is presently responsible for managing Tank-Automotive Command's reliability programs. He supervises a staff of fifty personnel, and provides support to all the project managers at TACOM. In the past, Mr. Jokubaitis has held positions as Director of Product Assurance, TARCOM; Director of US/FRG's main battle tank programs, and as Project Engineer for the Sheridan weapons system and Shillelagh missile projects. He has lectured RAM at the University of Arizona, has written articles in numerous magazines, and made presentations during RAM symposiums and seminars to include the 1983 Annual Reliability and Maintainability Symposium.

Michael F. Quinn
RAM Assessment Branch
U. S. Army Tank-Automotive Command
ATTN: AMSTA-QRA
Warren, Michigan 48397-5000 USA

Mr. Quinn is currently assigned as a General Engineer in the TACOM Product Assurance and Test Directorate. He has been with the government agency for eight years. Prior to that, he was in private industry for thirty years as a Product Engineer, Reliability Engineer, and Systems Engineer on both commercial and defense programs. Mr. Quinn's undergraduate training was at Xavier University and General Motors Institute and graduate studies at Butler University. He is also a graduate of the Industrial College of the Armed Forces.

Fig. 1 Defining Reliability

Fig. 2 Task Team Solution

COMPONENT	MAF	MA	
STORAGE BATTERIES	X	X	
WIRE HARNESS	X	X	
TRACK SHOES	X	X	
GUNNER'S PRIMARY SIGHT	X	X	ONLY WHEN BOTH
GUNNER'S AUXILIARY SIGHT	X		
COMMANDER'S WEAPON STATION SIGHT	X		
LASER RF	X		
TORSION BAR	X	X	ONLY IF BOTH #1 & #6 BREAK

REDUNDANCY (next to GUNNER'S PRIMARY SIGHT)
 REDUNDANCY DEGRADATION (next to COMMANDER'S WEAPON STATION SIGHT)
 DEGRADATION (next to TORSION BAR)

Fig. 3 FD/SC Matrix Example for AGS

Fig. 4 Reliability Requirement

<u>TECHNICAL</u>	<u>MILESTONE IIIA (END OF FSD)</u>	<u>MILESTONE III (END OF IPT)</u>
MISSION ABORT (MMBHMA)	266	319
MISSION AFFECTING (MMBHMAF)	122	147
MR		0.13
 <u>OPERATIONAL</u>		
MISSION ABORT (MMBOMA)	187	225
MISSION AFFECTING (MMBOMAF)	87	104
MR		0.17

Fig. 5 RAM Requirements Example (Armored Gun System)

Fig. 6 Monetary RAM Incentives

Fig. 7 Incentivizing Reliability

Fig. 8 Automation in R Tracking

Fig. 9 Purifying Field Data